

SOME ISSUES OF IMPROVING THE PROVISION OF BUSINESS TERMS IN UZBEKISTAN-ENGLISH TRANSLATION DICTIONARIES

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ANNOTATION

This article is devoted to some problems in the provision of business terms in Uzbek-English translation dictionaries, and it presents the obstacles to the provision of translation of terms in English and possible solutions to them.

Keywords: business terms, translation into English, situational context, electronic dictionaries

Introduction: Improving dictionaries, whether they are printed or in the form of a special program, always remains relevant. Providing translations of terms further complicates this need. Today, terms are enriched by borrowing words from other languages and creating internal words. The main factor determining the stability of the terminological system of a particular field is its organization and regularity. Therefore, in all languages with a certain degree of stabilization of terminology, terms are constantly organized. Organization is carried out on the basis of certain terminological standards.

There are problems in translating university administrative terms from English to Hausa. There are variations in the translation of the terms “Chancellor”, “Pro-chancellor” and “Vice-chancellor” in speeches, interviews and media translations. The aim of this study is to find better interpretations in translating university administrative terms. The specific objectives of the study are: (i) to identify different interpretations of the three terms; (ii) to identify better interpretations of the terms in accordance with certain established theoretical concepts and socio-cultural norms of the Hausa receptor language. The study is qualitative in nature, focusing on “situational context” and “cultural context” in data collection and analysis, using Halliday’s (2014) theoretical concept of systemic functional linguistics (SFL). The findings of the study included: (i) the three terms, Chancellor, Pro-Chancellor and Vice-Chancellor, have differences in translation among Hausa speakers and media organizations; (ii) using the context of the Hausa receptor language situation and culture, Chancellor is translated as Uban Jamiya, Pro-Chancellor is Shabangon

Majansha Kudanwanwa ta Jamiya and Pro-Chancellor is Shabangon Jamiya. The study shows that functional and pragmatic approaches to translation, using Halliday's (2014) theory of Systematic Functional Linguistics, have been effective in revealing meaning by using contextual variables of language rather than being limited to linguistic context alone.

Main part: Translators, like any other profession, face challenges. There are many challenges that experienced professionals in this field face, and new translators find them much more challenging. John Dryden's famous metaphor compares translation to dancing on ropes with tied feet (Dryden in Ross 2012), other sources compare translation to turning wine into water or to decanting without spilling, and translators are compared to gladiators in pajamas. Finally, Robert M. Grant argues that there can never be a completely final translation (Baker and Saldanha 2007). All of the above comparisons are expressive and/or humorous ways of characterizing translation as a complex and difficult task. Moreover, as the texts that students of the Institute of Applied Linguistics of RTU deal with, "the complexity increases when the text in question is specialized".

One of the most important tasks of translators in ensuring adequate quality translation is to be aware of the problems that may be encountered during the translation process and to be prepared to solve them. Opinions may differ on what constitutes adequate quality translation, but according to Hatim and Munday (2004: 10), the consensus is that "the literal expression of meaning, adherence to form, and emphasis on general accuracy" are essential. As one of the students who participated in this study noted, "The person reading your translation should not have to struggle too much to get its message, so the translation should be simple and understandable, but translating is a very complex task" that is simple and understandable enough for the target readers, while at the same time including all the specific details relevant to the text area or field, that is, to make the translation clear and attractive at the same time. The reader should understand the logic of the text.

Terminology problems related to Uzbek-English dictionaries manifest themselves in various aspects. The main issues and references are listed below:

Some connectives and terms in dictionaries are incorrectly or incorrectly translated. These problems arise, in particular, when determining equivalence and homonymy. The articles evaluate these issues lexicographically, including the differences in connectives in Uzbek and English.

Some dictionaries do not sufficiently cover widely used lexical combinations. For example, new terms or industry terms are not sufficiently defined or correctly cited.

The dictionary published by the Ijod-Press publishing house has tried to present such key terms in an orderly manner.

Electronic and printed dictionaries differ in terms of vocabulary. For example, Hasanboy Rasulov's English-Uzbek dictionary contains 26,500 words, and it is convenient to use it in electronic format for language learning. Printed dictionaries are often presented in alphabetical order, but in practical terms, search engines in electronic format are more effective for users. Electronic dictionaries, such as those proposed by Hasanboy Rasulov in the format of mobile applications, are preferred for modern users.

There are several problems in translating Uzbek business terms into English, which can be grouped as follows:

The meanings behind the terms in English and Uzbek may not correspond to the cultural and legal contexts. For example, when translating "finance department", the expression "finance department" may not reflect the specifics of the Uzbek system. Business terms are often specific to their field, and it is difficult to maintain precise meanings when translating. For example, "payroll report" can be translated as "payroll report", but in other contexts "salary report" may be appropriate. Misunderstandings arise when adapting abbreviations used in Uzbek to English. For example, it may not be clear to express "BHM" ("basic calculation unit") in English as "basic calculation unit"

Solutions and suggestions:

- Use descriptive translation: For words that do not have equivalents, descriptive translation is preferable (for example, "Copyright").
- Consult with experts: For accurate translation of terms specific to each field, it is necessary to use the help of experts in the field.
- Create multilingual dictionaries: Specialized dictionaries should be developed to increase compatibility between English and Uzbek

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